

Empowering Libraries, Connecting Communities

Innovation, Collaboration and Entrepreneurship

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Foreword

With great enthusiasm, I introduce the conference proceedings for "Empowering Libraries, Connecting Communities: Innovation, Collaboration, and Entrepreneurship." This conference marks a significant milestone in our ongoing exploration of the profound change occurring within the realm of libraries and their crucial role in society.

Libraries have always been bastions of knowledge, serving as repositories of our collective wisdom and heritage. However, libraries have evolved far beyond their traditional role in today's rapidly changing world. They have embraced innovation as a guiding principle, recognised collaboration as an essential strategy, and celebrated entrepreneurship as a driving force for positive change.

In this conference, we come together as a community of scholars, librarians, educators, and visionaries to examine and celebrate the ways in which libraries have metamorphosed into dynamic and inclusive centres of empowerment. Libraries have expanded into digital domains, embracing emerging technologies to serve their communities better.

The papers within these proceedings reflect the rich tapestry of ideas, initiatives, and experiences that have emerged from collective wisdom and thought. They explore the innovative ways libraries harness technology, such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and data analytics, to enhance access to information and provide immersive learning experiences.

As you read through these conference proceedings, you will discover a wealth of insights, best practices, and case studies that exemplify the remarkable journey libraries have embarked upon.

I congratulate the contributors for their valuable work. I congratulate the IMT Ghaziabad Library and Management Libraries Network for creating a platform to exchange these ideas. Together, we embark on a journey to shape the future of libraries, one that is inclusive, technologically advanced, and deeply connected to the communities they serve.

May these proceedings serve as a source of inspiration, a reference for best practices, and a catalyst for further innovation. Undoubtedly, this will contribute significantly to the ongoing dialogue about how libraries can continue to empower individuals and connect communities in an increasingly dynamic and interconnected world.

Vishal Talwar
Director
IMT Ghaziabad

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Mobile Phone Use and Smartphone Vision Syndrome in Today's Professionals

Nitesh Singh Pawar* & Calwin Rose**

ABSTRACT

Long-term use of smartphones, tablets, or other digital devices can cause a variety of symptoms collectively known as Smartphone Vision Syndrome, Digital Eye Strain, or Computer Vision Syndrome. The effects of lack of sleep on a person's ability to focus on their work are often overlooked. Staring at screens up close for long periods of time, as is common when using smartphones and similar devices, can cause eye strain and other vision problems. The development of Smartphone Vision Syndrome can be attributed to a number of variables. The light emitted by smartphones can reduce the body's natural generation of melatonin and interfere with sleep. Prolonged exposure to blue light is also associated with issues with eyestrain and headaches. Glare from screens can be tiring and irritating to the eyes. Using a smartphone outdoors or in a well-lit room might cause eye strain due to the high level of contrast between the screen and the environment. Reading tiny text or viewing small graphics on a smartphone screen can induce eye strain since more of the brain's resources must be used to focus on the content.

The Recent incidents of "Smartphone Vision Syndrome" in India.

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2. <https://www.dnaindia.com/health/report-what-is-smartphone-vision-syndrome-serious-disease-that-can-make-you-lose-your-eyesight-3023806>

In another news by The Hindu: 30,000 children are reporting blurred vision every year in India, says experts. Poor diet, prolonged exposure to mobile phones and TV among reasons, says Dr. Agarwal February 17, 2023 07:36 am | Updated 10:19 am IST - V. Thanmai & G. Rajya Lakshmi ;About 30,000 cases of child visual impairment were being reported every year, and the number was increasing, said Amar Agarwal, chairman, Dr. Agarwal's Eye Hospitals, who was in the city for inauguration of their new hospital recently. According to a study, the reason for such a large number of children suffering from blurred vision was malnutrition, consanguineous marriages, and prolonged watching of mobile phones and television. "Many people are

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Explanation of the whole idea of Smartphone Vision Syndrome

Prolonged use of digital devices like computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones can cause a variety of eye and vision-related issues collectively known as "Computer Vision Syndrome." And specially in terms of Mobile phones it's called "Mobile Vision Syndrome" "There are a number of potential side effects from staring at a mobile screen for long periods of time. The term "Mobile Vision Syndrome" refers to a group of symptoms that occur when a person is exposed to a mobile program.

Some common symptoms of Mobile Vision Syndrome include:

Eye strain: Discomfort, soreness, or fatigue in the eyes.

Dry eyes: Insufficient blinking and reduced tear production due to prolonged screen use.

Blurred vision: Difficulty in maintaining clear vision or experiencing temporary blurriness.

Headaches: Recurrent headaches, often associated with eye strain.

Neck and shoulder pain: Poor posture and sustained muscle tension from hunching over devices.

Difficulty focusing: Trouble shifting focus between screen and other distances, leading to eye fatigue.

Several factors contribute to Mobile Vision Syndrome, including:

Screen glare: Reflections and glare from the screen surface can cause eye discomfort.

Blue light exposure: Digital devices emit high-energy visible (HEV) blue light, which may contribute to eye strain and disrupt sleep patterns.

Viewing distance: Holding smartphones at closer distances than other screens can increase the demands on eye focusing.

Poor ergonomics: Awkward postures and inadequate support during device use can lead to musculoskeletal strain.

Why do issues with vision arise?

Several factors and disorders affecting the eyes and visual system might contribute to visual impairments. The most common causes of vision impairment are as follows:

Refractive Errors: The majority of cases of impaired vision can be attributed to refractive defects. They manifest when the eye's structure disrupts the normal path of light on its way to the retina, leading to distorted hazy vision. The most common kinds of refractive mistakes are:

Myopia (near-sightedness): Difficulty seeing distant objects clearly.

Hyperopia (farsightedness): Difficulty seeing nearby objects clearly.

Astigmatism: Blurred vision caused by an irregularly shaped cornea or lens.

Presbyopia: This is a natural age-related condition that typically occurs around the age of 40. It affects the eye's ability to focus on close objects, resulting in difficulty reading or performing tasks at close range.

Eye Diseases and Conditions: Various eye diseases and conditions can cause vision problems. Some examples include:

Cataracts: Clouding of the lens, resulting in blurred or hazy vision.

Glaucoma: Damage to the optic nerve, usually caused by increased eye pressure, leading to gradual loss of peripheral vision.

Age-related Macular Degeneration (AMD): Degeneration of the macula, the central part of the retina, leading to a loss of central vision.

Diabetic Retinopathy: Damage to the blood vessels in the retina due to diabetes, causing vision loss.

Eye Strain and Fatigue: Prolonged use of digital screens, reading in poor lighting conditions, or extended periods of focusing on near objects can strain the eyes and lead to symptoms such as eye fatigue, dryness, and blurred vision.

Injuries and Trauma: Physical injuries to the eyes, head, or face can cause vision problems depending on the severity and location of the injury.

Genetics and Family History: Some vision problems have a genetic component and can run in families. Conditions like myopia or certain eye diseases may have a hereditary component.

Systemic Health Conditions: Certain systemic health conditions, such as diabetes or hypertension, can affect the blood vessels in the eyes and lead to vision problems if not properly managed.

It is important to note that this is not an exhaustive list, and there can be other factors contributing to vision-related problems. If you are experiencing any vision problems or concerns, it is recommended to consult with an eye care professional for a comprehensive examination and appropriate diagnosis.

Research Method: To conduct this research, a systematic review of relevant literature was performed. The search strategy involved utilizing a combination of keywords, such as "Smartphone Vision Syndrome," "Digital Eye Strain," "Computer Vision Syndrome," "Mobile Phone Use," and "Professionals." These keywords were chosen to ensure the inclusion of articles relevant to the impact of smartphone usage on visual health among professionals.

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articles written in English to ensure accessibility to the wider scientific community. We aimed to ensure that emerging topics and recent developments related to Smartphone Vision Syndrome (SVS) and its impact on professional populations were adequately represented in our analysis. The initial search process yielded a total of 1780 relevant articles. Upon further review and scrutiny, 38 open access articles were included in the final analysis in summary, the survey approach fortified the findings and substantiated the conclusions drawn from the selected studies, shedding light on the prevalence, risk factors, symptoms, and management of SVS in professional populations.

To prevent or alleviate Smartphone Vision Syndrome, consider the following tips:

Take regular breaks: Follow the 20-20-20 guideline and schedule regular breaks. You should take a 20 second break every 20 minutes to stare at something at least 20 feet away. As a result, your eyes will experience less strain.

Source: Internet.

Adjust Screen brightness: Adjust the screen's brightness to a level that's easy for your eyes, and stay away from extremes of light and darkness when using your smartphone.

Source: Internet.

Minimize blue light exposure: Use the “night mode” or “blue light filter” on your smartphone, or look into apps that are designed to minimize the quantity of blue light output, to keep your exposure to this type of light to a minimum. The intensity of blue light can be adjusted with the help of in-built features in some devices.

Increase font size: Text on your smartphone can be made larger if you want to read it without squinting or straining your eyes.

Maintain good posture: Keep an upright posture by holding your smartphone at arm's length and an arm's length away from your body. Try not to strain your neck too much while using a mobile device.

CHECK YOUR BODY POSTURE

USING SMARTPHONE/TABLET

Blink frequently: To prevent your eyes from drying out, it is important to blink frequently while using your smartphone.

Use proper Ergonomics: Employ correct ergonomics by placing your monitor at eye level, utilizing a supportive chair, and keeping the correct distance between you and the screen.

Use blue light filters: Enable blue light filters or make use of specialist apps to lessen the quantity of blue light your screens emit.

Consider computer eyewear: Think about getting some computer glasses, whether they're prescription or not; they may help lessen eye strain.

Create a conducive environment: Make the space comfortable by adjusting the lighting so that it's neither too bright nor too dim to cause eye strain.

Practice eye exercises: Exercise your eyes regularly to strengthen and relax your eye muscles. Blinking exercises, staring at faraway things, and eye rolls are all examples of acceptable eye workouts.

Regular eye exams: Schedule regular eye check-ups to detect any underlying vision problems and receive appropriate treatment if necessary. Remember, while these tips can help alleviate the symptoms of Smartphone Vision Syndrome, it's also important to practice moderation and limit excessive screen time to promote overall eye health.

It is recommended to speak with an eye care specialist for tailored guidance, especially if you are experiencing persistent or severe symptoms, even though these techniques can help lessen the effects of screen time. The health of your eyes and body as a whole can benefit from exercise, a well-rounded diet, and frequent pauses from screen time.

Prevention is better than cure: Best way to reducing Your Screen Time

There are many ways in which reducing screen time might improve health. Here are some proven strategies for limiting your time in front of electronic screens:

Set goals and limits: Limit your time in front of the screen and establish concrete goals for cutting back. Reduce screen time gradually to make the change easier on yourself and your family.

Track your screen time: Learn how much time you spend on digital devices by keeping track of it with an app or the built-in feature on your smartphone. This might be useful for seeing trends and pinpointing places to make reductions.

Establish device-free zones and times: Set device-free zones and times: Make certain parts of your home or specific periods of the day off-limits for using electronic gadgets. Create technology-free zones in the bedroom, for instance, to improve your quality of sleep.

Create alternative activities: Instead of spending time on digital media, try your hand at some of the many other things out there. Doing things like reading books, pursuing hobbies, going outside, getting exercise, and hanging out with friends and family all count.

Practice mindful screen use: Be intentional about your screen time, both in terms of its duration and its intended purpose. Consciously choose activities that offer value or productivity to your life and reduce mindless scrolling and recreational screen time.

Plan screen-free breaks: Schedule time away from screens; make this a regular part of your day. Take this time to do something that doesn't require a screen, like going for a walk, meditating, or working on a creative project.

Use screen time management tools: Leverage the capabilities of your smartphone, tablet, or computer that help you limit your screen

time or receive alerts when you've reached a present limit.

Encourage offline interactions: Promote face-to-face communication by setting an example of doing so with friends, family, and co-workers. Reduce your dependency on digital communication by prioritizing in-person interactions, such as conversations, group activities, and social gatherings.

Practice digital detoxes: Use “digital detoxes,” or periods of time (weekends, vacations) during which you refrain from using any electronic gadgets at all. Take advantage of this lull in activity to rest, relax, and reconnect with the world.

Seek support and accountability: Get help from those who believe in you and hold you accountable by enlisting the help of loved ones and those who share your ambitions. Encourage one another and hold each other accountable to decreasing screen time.

Keep in mind that striking a balance that benefits your life as a whole is of utmost importance. By putting these into practice gradually, you can help yourself cut down on screen time and establish better routines.

Five Eye-Improving Moves You Can Do at Your Workplace or Anywhere

Maintaining healthy vision is only one of the many benefits of a physically active lifestyle. The following are some of the most popular ways to improve your vision while on the road.

Eye Rolls: First, roll your eyes and stare straight ahead. Then, for a few seconds, roll your eyes slowly in a clockwise direction. To continue, turn them counter clockwise. This practice can be repeated multiple times to help with eye mobility and stress relief.

Blinking: The simple act of blinking can relieve dry eyes and improve visual comfort. Our natural tendency to blink lessens when using digital devices or concentrating hard. Take roughly 20 seconds out of your day to

deliberately blink your eyes rapidly. To maintain healthy eye moisture, you should perform this activity at regular intervals throughout the day.

Distance Focus: Focus your eyes on something far away, such a tree or a building, for a few seconds. Then, look down at something close by, like your hand or a pen, and stare at it intently for a few seconds. To practice shifting your attention and lessen eye strain, repeat this exercise while looking at items both near and far away.

Palming: Palming entails making a lot of friction by rubbing one's hands together. After your hands have warmed up, close your eyes and rest your palms over them, being careful not to press on your eyes. Calm down, take some deep breaths, and let the comforting darkness and heat wash over your weary eyes. This is a great stress-buster and eye-strain reliever.

Figure Eight: Think of a big figure eight (8) around 10 feet in front of you. Follow the horizontal and vertical lines of the figure eight with your eyes. Pay attention to the fluidity of your eye movements as you follow the contours of the body. The flexibility and coordination of your eyes will benefit from this workout.

Keep in mind that the goal here is for these exercises to be something you can do quickly and easily while traveling. However, maintaining overall eye health requires routine visits to an eye care specialist, a healthy lifestyle, and adherence to any suggestions made for your unique visual requirements.

Conclusion: A Survival Guide

Like many other professionals, librarians can take measures to protect themselves against Smartphone Vision Syndrome and digital eye strain. The following are some precautions librarians can take to avoid these hazards: Take frequent pauses from screen time, as recommended by the 20-20-20 rule. You should take a 20 second break every 20 minutes to stare at something at least 20 feet away. This eases the stress on your eyes and gives them a

break. The viewing experience on your screens can be improved by adjusting the brightness, contrast, and font size. Don't put your eyes through the effort of staring at a screen that's too bright or too dark. Make sure you're sitting correctly while using a computer or other digital device. Make sure the screen is at eye level and your chair has good back support. Your neck, shoulders, and back will thank you for this. Remember to blink often, especially when staring at a screen for long periods of time. It's important to blink frequently to prevent dryness and irritation of the eyes.

Make sure your office is well-lit and you're able to see what you're doing. Don't expose your eyes to unnecessary strain by working in glaring sunlight or pitch darkness. If you need to shed light on a specific location, a task including breaks into your schedule and doing new things that don't require you to stare at a screen. During your breaks, get up and move about, close your eyes, and focus on anything else to give your eyes a rest.

Maintain routine professional eye examinations as part of your comprehensive approach to eye health. They are qualified to examine your eyes, identify any pre-existing issues, and treat them or provide proper vision correction if necessary. Always pay attention to what your body is telling you and make any necessary adjustments to your routine. Consult an eye care specialist for individualized advice and guidance if your symptoms persist or worsen.

Suggestions: The research results bring to light the urgent necessity of addressing Smartphone Vision Syndrome (SVS) among professionals. Prolonged exposure to screens and the blue light emitted by smartphones wreak havoc on our circadian rhythms, leading to sleep disruptions and overwhelming fatigue. Furthermore, the adoption of poor visual habits, like holding phones at peculiar angles and forgetting to blink, only compounds the discomfort and strain on our eyes.

To combat these adverse effects, integrating preventive measures becomes paramount. The 20-20-20 rule stands as an essential reminder, urging professionals to take a mere 20-second breather every 20 minutes, shifting their focus to an object positioned 20 feet away. Tinkering with screen settings—brightness, font size, and the like—provides a gateway to visual bliss, easing strain and enhancing overall comfort

EYES are forever : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=malQyromQfI>

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Take regular breaks: Follow the 20-20-20 guideline and schedule regular breaks. You should take a 20 second break every 20 minutes to stare at something at least 20 feet away. As a result, your eyes will experience less strain.

Source: Internet.

Adjust Screen brightness: Adjust the screen's brightness to a level that's easy for your eyes, and stay away from extremes of light and darkness when using your smartphone.

Source: Internet.

Minimize blue light exposure: Use the “night mode” or “blue light filter” on your smartphone, or look into apps that are designed to minimize the quantity of blue light output, to keep your exposure to this type of light to a minimum. The intensity of blue light can be adjusted with the help of in-built features in some devices.

Increase font size: Text on your smartphone can be made larger if you want to read it without squinting or straining your eyes.

Maintain good posture: Keep an upright posture by holding your smartphone at arm’s length and an arm’s length away from your body. Try not to strain your neck too much while using a mobile device.

Blink frequently: To prevent your eyes from drying out, it is important to blink frequently while using your smartphone.

Use proper Ergonomics: Employ correct ergonomics by placing your monitor at eye level, utilizing a supportive chair, and keeping the correct distance between you and the screen.

Use blue light filters: Enable blue light filters or make use of specialist apps to lessen the quantity of blue light your screens emit.

Consider computer eyewear: Think about getting some computer glasses, whether they’re prescription or not; they may help lessen eye strain.

Create a conducive environment: Make the space comfortable by adjusting the lighting so that it’s neither too bright nor too dim to cause eye strain.

Practice eye exercises: Exercise your eyes regularly to strengthen and relax your eye muscles. Blinking exercises, staring at faraway things, and eye rolls are all examples of acceptable eye workouts.

Regular eye exams: Schedule regular eye check-ups to detect any underlying vision problems and receive appropriate treatment if necessary. Remember, while these tips can help alleviate the symptoms of Smartphone Vision Syndrome, it’s also important to practice moderation and limit excessive screen time to promote overall eye health.

It is recommended to speak with an eye care specialist for tailored guidance, especially if you are experiencing persistent or severe symptoms, even though these techniques can help lessen the effects of screen time. The health of your eyes and body as a whole can benefit from exercise, a well-rounded diet, and frequent pauses from screen time.

Prevention is better than cure: Best way to reducing Your Screen Time

There are many ways in which reducing screen time might improve health. Here are some proven strategies for limiting your time in front of electronic screens:

Set goals and limits: Limit your time in front of the screen and establish concrete goals for cutting back. Reduce screen time gradually to make the change easier on yourself and your family.

Track your screen time: Learn how much time you spend on digital devices by keeping track of it with an app or the built-in feature on your smartphone. This might be useful for seeing trends and pinpointing places to make reductions.

Establish device-free zones and times: Set device-free zones and times: Make certain parts of your home or specific periods of the day off-limits for using electronic gadgets. Create technology-free zones in the bedroom, for instance, to improve your quality of sleep.

Create alternative activities: Instead of spending time on digital media, try your hand at some of the many other things out there. Doing things like reading books, pursuing hobbies, going outside, getting exercise, and hanging out with friends and family all count.

Practice mindful screen use: Be intentional about your screen time, both in terms of its duration and its intended purpose. Consciously choose activities that offer value or productivity to your life and reduce mindless scrolling and recreational screen time.

Plan screen-free breaks: Schedule time away from screens; make this a regular part of your day. Take this time to do something that doesn't require a screen, like going for a walk, meditating, or working on a creative project.

Use screen time management tools: Leverage the capabilities of your smartphone, tablet, or computer that help you limit your screen

time or receive alerts when you've reached a present limit.

Encourage offline interactions: Promote face-to-face communication by setting an example of doing so with friends, family, and co-workers. Reduce your dependency on digital communication by prioritizing in-person interactions, such as conversations, group activities, and social gatherings.

Practice digital detoxes: Use "digital detoxes," or periods of time (weekends, vacations) during which you refrain from using any electronic gadgets at all. Take advantage of this lull in activity to rest, relax, and reconnect with the world.

Seek support and accountability: Get help from those who believe in you and hold you accountable by enlisting the help of loved ones and those who share your ambitions. Encourage one another and hold each other accountable to decreasing screen time.

Keep in mind that striking a balance that benefits your life as a whole is of utmost importance. By putting these into practice gradually, you can help yourself cut down on screen time and establish better routines.

Five Eye-Improving Moves You Can Do at Your Workplace or Anywhere

Maintaining healthy vision is only one of the many benefits of a physically active lifestyle. The following are some of the most popular ways to improve your vision while on the road.

Eye Rolls: First, roll your eyes and stare straight ahead. Then, for a few seconds, roll your eyes slowly in a clockwise direction. To continue, turn them counter clockwise. This practice can be repeated multiple times to help with eye mobility and stress relief.

Blinking: The simple act of blinking can relieve dry eyes and improve visual comfort. Our natural tendency to blink lessens when using digital devices or concentrating hard. Take roughly 20 seconds out of your day to

deliberately blink your eyes rapidly. To maintain healthy eye moisture, you should perform this activity at regular intervals throughout the day.

Distance Focus: Focus your eyes on something far away, such as a tree or a building, for a few seconds. Then, look down at something close by, like your hand or a pen, and stare at it intently for a few seconds. To practice shifting your attention and lessen eye strain, repeat this exercise while looking at items both near and far away.

Palming: Palming entails making a lot of friction by rubbing one's hands together. After your hands have warmed up, close your eyes and rest your palms over them, being careful not to press on your eyes. Calm down, take some deep breaths, and let the comforting darkness and heat wash over your weary eyes. This is a great stress-buster and eye-strain reliever.

Figure Eight: Think of a big figure eight (8) around 10 feet in front of you. Follow the horizontal and vertical lines of the figure eight with your eyes. Pay attention to the fluidity of your eye movements as you follow the contours of the body. The flexibility and coordination of your eyes will benefit from this workout.

Keep in mind that the goal here is for these exercises to be something you can do quickly and easily while traveling. However, maintaining overall eye health requires routine visits to an eye care specialist, a healthy lifestyle, and adherence to any suggestions made for your unique visual requirements.

Conclusion: A Survival Guide

Like many other professionals, librarians can take measures to protect themselves against Smartphone Vision Syndrome and digital eye strain. The following are some precautions librarians can take to avoid these hazards: Take frequent pauses from screen time, as recommended by the 20-20-20 rule. You should take a 20 second break every 20 minutes to stare at something at least 20 feet away. This eases the stress on your eyes and gives them a

break. The viewing experience on your screens can be improved by adjusting the brightness, contrast, and font size. Don't put your eyes through the effort of staring at a screen that's too bright or too dark. Make sure you're sitting correctly while using a computer or other digital device. Make sure the screen is at eye level and your chair has good back support. Your neck, shoulders, and back will thank you for this. Remember to blink often, especially when staring at a screen for long periods of time. It's important to blink frequently to prevent dryness and irritation of the eyes.

Make sure your office is well-lit and you're able to see what you're doing. Don't expose your eyes to unnecessary strain by working in glaring sunlight or pitch darkness. If you need to shed light on a specific location, a task light is your best bet. Work more efficiently by including breaks into your schedule and doing new things that don't require you to stare at a screen. During your breaks, get up and move about, close your eyes, and focus on anything else to give your eyes a rest.

Maintain routine professional eye examinations as part of your comprehensive approach to eye health. They are qualified to examine your eyes, identify any pre-existing issues, and treat them or provide proper vision correction if necessary. Always pay attention to what your body is telling you and make any necessary adjustments to your routine. Consult an eye care specialist for individualized advice and guidance if your symptoms persist or worsen.

Suggestions: The research results bring to light the urgent necessity of addressing Smartphone Vision Syndrome (SVS) among professionals. Prolonged exposure to screens and the blue light emitted by smartphones wreak havoc on our circadian rhythms, leading to sleep disruptions and overwhelming fatigue. Furthermore, the adoption of poor visual habits, like holding phones at peculiar angles and forgetting to blink, only compounds the discomfort and strain on our eyes.

To combat these adverse effects, integrating preventive measures becomes paramount. The 20-20-20 rule stands as an essential reminder, urging professionals to take a mere 20-second breather every 20 minutes, shifting their focus to an object positioned 20 feet away. Tinkering with screen settings – brightness, font size, and the like – provides a gateway to visual bliss, easing strain and enhancing overall comfort

EYES are forever : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=malQyromQfI>

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